

Simulation of Array Tilt Effects in Laser Phased Arrays

Jack E. McCrae, Jr.
Air Force Institute of Technology
Department of Engineering Physics
Center for Directed Energy (AFIT/CDE)
2950 Hobson Way
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-7765

and
Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education,
1299 Bethel Valley Road, Oak Ridge, TN, 37830
937-255-3636 x4739
jack.mccrae.ctr@afit.edu

Steven T. Fiorino
Air Force Institute of Technology
Department of Engineering Physics
Center for Directed Energy (AFIT/CDE)
2950 Hobson Way
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-7765
937-255-3636 x4506
steven.fiorino@afit.edu

Abstract— A coherent laser array can be phased through the turbulent atmosphere on target based upon the laser light scattered from that target. For some system concepts, the transmitter array tilt cannot be determined by this phasing process. The expected distribution of array tilt values is examined here for randomly phased arrays. When certain presumptions about phase are taken, as the array grows in number of elements the effect of the array tilt aberration on peak irradiance diminishes, while the pointing error remains near the diffraction limited spot size. These results have potentially important consequences for system design. They highlight the necessity of a method to handle the array tilt aberration for small systems which demand near ideal performance, while simultaneously suggesting array tilt may be ignorable for large systems or systems operating in environments where near diffraction limited performance is already unachievable due to turbulence or jitter.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. METHODOLOGY	1
3. RESULTS.....	3
4. CONCLUSIONS	6
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	6
REFERENCES.....	7
BIOGRAPHIES.....	7

1. INTRODUCTION

Phased arrays are an attractive route to high energy laser systems and promise new capabilities. These new capabilities include electronic beam steering, electronic focusing, atmospheric compensation, and simultaneous multiple beams. [1,2,3,4] Phased arrays also present new challenges in engineering and science.

The issue of array tilt is one challenge which arises. Array tilt is just wavefront tilt discretized over the elements of a phased array. Array tilt is also referred to as stair-mode since it can look like a staircase when plotted with phase as height. Tyler [5] has pointed out that a system can be phased on a target based on the scattered speckle return, but that the telescope array tilt will be an unobservable quantity in certain relevant cases.

Previous work has investigated the performance impact this array tilt aberration might have on system performance as a function of the amount of array tilt present.[6,7] This present effort attempts to quantify the amount of array tilt that is likely to be present for systems which use object based phasing.

2. METHODOLOGY

Approach

The purpose of this study is to investigate the distribution of the array tilts remaining when target-in-the-loop phasing is used to command a laser array. This study tries to be indifferent to beam control system implementation details by evaluating the array tilt present on randomly phased arrays.

Centimeters are probably a reasonable unit for discussing phased array sizes for potential high energy laser systems. Sub-apertures might be a few centimeters in diameter, and an entire array might be tens of centimeters across. Van Zandt discusses tactically interesting phased – and unphased – arrays further.[8] For an array of this size, we can expect many waves of phase difference between sub-aperture wavefronts on initial assembly. In operation if mounted on an aircraft or other moving platform, many waves of drift between these phases can also be expected in the absence of some active control scheme. For these reasons, it seems reasonable to propose that the phases between sub-apertures are completely random. Since phase will only need to be defined modulo 2π , we can then expect these phases to behave as uniformly distributed random variables over a 2π range.

Overview of Array Tilt

Fig. 1 shows a potential layout of a phased array aperture, with the sub-apertures numbered 1-7. This array is arranged on a hexagonal grid. Fig. 2 shows the intensity pattern an array like this would produce in the far-field in the absence of atmospheric or other aberrations, and with the sub-apertures all in phase at the target. For this particular case, 30 cm diameter sub-apertures with 1 cm gaps between them were simulated. Uniform intensity within and across the sub-apertures was also assumed. These particular details are

provided for completeness, and they influence the far-field patterns shown below, but they are unimportant to much of the analysis which follows.

Figure 1 – A 7 element phased array, with a sub-aperture numbering convention shown.

Figure 2 – The far-field intensity pattern from the 7 element array.

If a small amount of array tilt is present, the central lobe in the far-field pattern will move away from the center and sidelobes will grow behind this main lobe and decrease in front of this movement. Fig. 3 illustrates the phases associated with a small amount, δ , of array tilt on the x and y axes.

Figure 3 – Phases on the transmitter array for x -axis (a) and y -axis (b) array tilt.

Figure 4. illustrates the effect of $\frac{1}{4}$ wave of x -axis array tilt on the far-field pattern. That is δ in fig. 3a is set to $\frac{1}{4}$ wave or $\pi/2$ radians.

Figure 4 – The far-field intensity pattern from the 7 element array with $\frac{1}{4}$ wave of x -axis array tilt present.

Array tilt on either the x or y axis can only grow to half a wave, after which it wraps around to negative half a wave. This is easily seen by imagining δ on fig. 3 set to π radians. Since phase is only defined modulo 2π , positive and negative π are the same phase. Also notice an array tilt of half a wave on x equals an array tilt of half a wave on y since the 2π phase shifts implied on fig. 3a become zero at this point. More precisely the array tilt aliases back to the center zone when the absolute value of the sum or difference of the x and y array tilts exceeds half a wave; this fact was examined by Hyde[7]. Fig. 5 shows the far field intensity pattern for this worst case. The main peak has split in two, and the peak intensity is only 54% of the unaberrated case. This ratio depends on array geometry details, so it is not a universal constant. Notice this array tilt can be viewed as resulting from a y -axis array tilt where the main peak has steered up until the peak behind it on the y -axis has reached an equal intensity, or it can be viewed as an x -axis array tilt, where the two largest sidelobes seen to the left of the main peak on fig. 2 have been steered to the right to become the pair of largest lobes.

Figure 5 – The far-field intensity pattern from the 7 element array with worst case array tilt present.

3. RESULTS

A Simple Linear Model

If phase is treated as a real number between $+\pi$ and $-\pi$, then the phases on the array can be handled linearly and decomposed into different modes. One set of modes frequently used in optics is Zernike modes which are orthogonal on the unit disk. When the Zernike modes are projected onto the 7 element array used here, only 7 modes are needed to completely describe the phase. Fig. 6 shows one choice of a matrix of sub-aperture weights to decompose phases on the transmitter into Zernike-like modes. The rows of this matrix are mutually orthogonal and the matrix is invertible, so this decomposition is unique and reversible.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 2 & 0 & -2 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & -6 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & -2 & 0 & -2 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} \text{piston} \\ \text{x tilt} \\ \text{y tilt} \\ \text{focus} \\ \text{oblique astigmatism} \\ \text{vertical astigmatism} \\ \text{oblique trefoil} \end{matrix}$$

Figure 6 – Sub-aperture weights for decomposition of transmitter phases into modes.

Notice the weights on the *x-tilt* and *y-tilt* rows match (to a sign) the multipliers of δ on fig. 3. If the dot-product of tilts shown on fig. 3 are computed against these rows the results are 12δ and 4δ respectively. Thus the *x-axis* array tilt can be computed for an arbitrary set of transmitter phases by computing this dot product and dividing by 12. The divisor weights for each of these modes can also be revealed by multiplying this matrix by its transpose and reading down the main diagonal.

If we start with random phases on the array, we can now compute the expected distribution of array tilts, or any of the other modes if desired. Phases, φ_i , distributed uniformly between $-\pi$ and $+\pi$, have a variance of:

$$\text{Var}(\varphi_i) = \frac{(2\pi)^2}{12} (\text{rad}^2) \quad (1)$$

The *y-axis* array tilt will be a sum of 4 of these random variables divided by 4. The sign of the weights doesn't matter to the distribution of array tilts since the random phases have zero mean, and dividing by 4 will cut the variance of each piece of this sum by 16. The *y-axis* array tilt variance will be the sum of these 4 subpart variances or:

$$\text{Var}(y \text{ tilt}) = \frac{(2\pi)^2}{4 \times 12} = \frac{\pi^2}{12} (\text{rad}^2) \quad (2)$$

The actual distribution of *y-axis* array tilt values would be

the convolution of all four uniform phase distributions. This distribution is a piecewise cubic function which is very close to Gaussian. Fig. 7 shows the distribution of results for *y-axis* array tilt from 100,000 cases of uniformly random phases 7 element arrays as detailed here compared with a Gaussian distribution with the variance computed above.

Figure 7 – Distribution of *y-axis* array tilt values for 7 element array and linear phase model compared with Gaussian

Evaluation of the *x-axis* array tilt follows similarly resulting in a variance of:

$$\text{Var}(x \text{ tilt}) = \frac{(2\pi)^2}{12 \times 12} = \frac{\pi^2}{36} (\text{rad}^2) \quad (3)$$

The actual distribution of *x-axis* array tilt values would be the convolution of six uniform phase distributions, but two of these distributions would be twice as large because of the weights. Again, this distribution is approaching a Gaussian. Fig. 8 shows the distribution of results for *x-axis* array tilt from 100,000 cases of uniformly random phases 7 element arrays as detailed here compared with a Gaussian distribution with the variance computed above.

Figure 8 – Distribution of *x-axis* array tilt values for 7 element array and linear phase model compared with Gaussian

An Improved Linear Model

A potential issue with the above approach becomes apparent as we allow the array size to grow. Array tilt is modeled above as a plane being fit to the data while the phase is held constrained between plus and minus π across the entire array. It is entirely possible that a much better fit to phase can be achieved by allowing the phase to unwrap as we cross the array. One way to approach this is letting the phase steps between elements be distributed between plus and minus π instead of the phases themselves. Fig. 9 shows such a scheme for evaluating the x -axis array tilt on the 7 element array.

Figure 9 – Improved array tilt evaluation scheme. Uniformly distributed random phase differences are located at the red arrows.

The x -axis array tilt can be computed as half of the average phase difference between adjacent elements along this direction. The factor of one-half is needed because the phase differences on fig. 3a are always 2δ between elements connected by arrows above. The expected distribution of x -axis array tilts will thus have $\frac{1}{4}$ the variance of what was computed for of y -axis array tilts via the simple linear method. That is:

$$Var(x \text{ tilt imp.}) = \frac{(2\pi)^2}{16 \times 12} = \frac{\pi^2}{48} \text{ (rad}^2\text{)} \quad (4)$$

Of course, simulating this distribution with 100,000 averages of 4 random phases leads to results which match a Gaussian just as well as in that previous case; this is shown on fig. 10.

Figure 10 – Distribution of x -array tilt values for 7 element array and improved linear phase model compared with Gaussian.

We could move on to y -axis array tilt using a similar method as well. Fig. 11 shows a scheme similar to that in fig. 9, but for y -axis array tilt in this case. There is a problem with this scheme however. Since the phases make closed loops, two phase difference values aren't independent since the sum of phases around these loops needs to be $2\pi n$ for some integer n . This could be most easily handled by assigning random phases first to each transmitter, then computing the differences and wrapping the results back to a range of plus or minus π .

Figure 11 – Possible y -axis array tilt evaluation scheme. Uniformly distributed random phase differences can't be independently assigned on all the red arrows.

A Non-linear model

Some of the above challenges disappear, and a new set of issues arises if phase is treated non-linearly. That is instead of treating phase as a real number between plus and minus π , it can be kept as a phasor, $e^{i\varphi}$, for as long as possible. If we, perhaps naively, evaluate array tilts as suggested above via this method we could write:

$$x \text{ tilt} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Arg} \left(e^{i\varphi_1} e^{-i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_3} e^{-i\varphi_4} + e^{i\varphi_4} e^{-i\varphi_5} + e^{i\varphi_6} e^{-i\varphi_7} \right) \quad (5)$$

If the phases above are uniformly distributed between plus and minus π , this approach clearly results in x-axis array tilts uniformly distributed between plus and minus $\pi/2$. It's also easy to see that this result wouldn't change as the array size is allowed to grow. However, this isn't exactly what we wish to compute. We would like to know the amount of array tilt left on the array after the observable modes have been removed. With a nonlinear definition of phase, we give up guarantees of uniqueness, invertibility, and orthogonality for mode decompositions. Now the order we remove modes will matter, and we need tools to remove each of these modes.

Each of the modes used in the linear model above can be expressed many ways in a phasor form which will well approximate the weighting functions from fig. 6 when the phase values are small. One set of functions which can accomplish this is given below, in the order they will be applied.

Oblique trefoil was computed with:

$$trefoil = Arg \left(e^{i\varphi_1 - i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_1 - i\varphi_3} + e^{i\varphi_5 - i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_5 - i\varphi_7} + e^{i\varphi_6 - i\varphi_7} + e^{i\varphi_6 - i\varphi_3} \right) \quad (6)$$

Vertical astigmatism was computed using:

$$vert. astig. = Arg \left(\left(e^{i\varphi_1} + e^{i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_6} + e^{i\varphi_7} \right) \times \left(e^{-i\varphi_3} + e^{-i\varphi_5} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

Oblique astigmatism was computed as:

$$obliq. astig. = Arg \left(\left(e^{i\varphi_1} + e^{i\varphi_7} \right) \times \left(e^{-i\varphi_2} + e^{-i\varphi_6} \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

Focus was computed through:

$$focus = Arg \left(\left(e^{i\varphi_1} + e^{i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_3} + e^{i\varphi_5} + e^{i\varphi_6} + e^{i\varphi_7} \right) \times e^{-i\varphi_4} \right) \quad (9)$$

Eq. 5 above was used to compute x tilt, and y tilt was computed as given in fig. 11, that is:

$$y tilt = Arg \left(e^{i\varphi_1 - i\varphi_3} + e^{i\varphi_1 - i\varphi_4} + e^{i\varphi_2 - i\varphi_4} + e^{i\varphi_2 - i\varphi_5} + e^{i\varphi_3 - i\varphi_6} + e^{i\varphi_4 - i\varphi_6} + e^{i\varphi_4 - i\varphi_7} + e^{i\varphi_4 - i\varphi_5} \right) \quad (10)$$

Finally, piston was computed via:

$$piston = Arg \left(e^{i\varphi_1} + e^{i\varphi_2} + e^{i\varphi_3} + e^{i\varphi_4} + e^{i\varphi_5} + e^{i\varphi_6} + e^{i\varphi_7} \right) \quad (11)$$

A small amount of each mode was applied to the array and the equations above were verified to accurately measure these modes. These modes were added based upon the weights from fig. 6, measured with the above. The orthogonality of these modes was investigated by checking to see if small amounts of one mode registered when any of the other equations were applied to it. Some small effects were noted. The only interaction noted larger than second order was between trefoil and x-tilt. From the definitions used, it can be discerned that trefoil will be perceived to have a small value for x-tilt. The converse didn't appear to be true. Since trefoil is to be projected away before x tilt is evaluated, this isn't expect to be an issue.

To study this nonlinear phase model, 100,000 instances of phases, uniformly distributed between plus and minus π , were created and the modes were projected out in the order given above. Fig. 12 shows the distribution of x-axis array tilt remaining after all modes above it had been removed. The results are compared with the Gaussian distribution derived for this case with the improved linear model. The agreement is very good, but perhaps not quite as good as for that prior case. There is no reason to expect this agreement, other than the discussion of the improved linear model above. Why that case seems to apply here isn't perfectly clear. The y tilt result didn't look Gaussian at all and won't be studied here.

Figure 12 – Distribution of x-axis array tilt values for 7 element array using non-linear phase model (histogram) compared with previous Gaussian model (curve).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Discussion of results

The simple and improved linear phase models presented predict the distributions of array tilt will decrease with increasing number of array elements. This is good news for phased array systems and suggests larger arrays may not need a separate system to address this aberration.

The simple linear model predicts the array tilt distribution will decrease quite quickly with increasing array size. A simple one dimensional analysis shows the array tilt variance will diminish like $1/n^3$, where n is the number of elements in the array. This model should be accurate for unwrapped phase, but on a discrete array with large phase steps between elements a reasonable definition of unwrapped phase probably doesn't exist.

The improved linear model also predicts the array tilt distribution will decrease with increasing array size. For this case, a one dimensional analysis shows the array tilt variance will diminish like $1/n$, where n is the number of elements in the array. It is very encouraging that the predictions of the improved linear model match the results of the non-linear array tilt estimate. This gives hope that real world results will be likewise.

It might be noticed that the simple linear model gave a greater x -axis array tilt variance than the improved linear model for the 7 element array cases. For small arrays this can be the case, but the trend will quickly reverse. If you consider two phases defined over plus and minus π , their difference can range between plus and minus 2π , the simple linear model treats phase this way, and thus the tilt variance predicted is increased somewhat. The improved linear model only looks at phase differences and keeps them between plus and minus π so this doesn't happen.

Future Work

This effort has only scratched the surface on this topic, and a lot of interesting work remains. Experimental demonstration of these ideas is of obvious importance, but also the hardest to realize. The non-linear model presented here needs more development. The non-linear mode decomposition used here was created by hand and is in no way optimized. With an optimal and automatic method to accomplish non-linear phase decomposition it would be easy to extend this work to much larger arrays.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded in part by a grant from the High Energy Laser Joint Technology Office (HEL JTO) and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (AFOSR). This research was supported in part by an appointment at the Air Force Institute of Technology administered by the Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education through an interagency agreement between the U.S. Department of Energy and AFIT. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the Air Force, the Department of Defense, or the U. S. Government.

REFERENCES

- [1] Brignon, A. (Ed.), [Coherent Laser Beam Combining], Wiley, (2013)
- [2] McManamon, P. F., Dorschner, T. A., Corkum, D. L., Friedman, L. J., Hobbs, D. S., Holz, M., Liberman, S., Nguyen, H. Q., Resler, D. P., Sharp, R. C., & Watson, E. A. (1996), "Optical phased array technology", Proceedings of the IEEE, 84(2), 268-298.
- [3] Motes, R. A. and Berdine R. W., [Introduction to High-Power Fiber Lasers], Directed Energy Professional Society, Albuquerque, New Mexico, 1-12 (2009).
- [4] Vorontsov, M. A., Kolosov, V. V., and Kohnle, A., "Adaptive laser beam projection on an extended target: phase- and field-conjugate precompensation", J. Opt. Soc. Am. A, 24(7), 1975 (2007).
- [5] Tyler, G. A. (2012). "Accommodation of speckle in object-based phasing", JOSA A, 29(5), 722-733.
- [6] Spencer, M. F., & Hyde, M. W. (2012, October). "An investigation of stair mode in optical phased arrays using tiled apertures", In SPIE Optical Engineering+ Applications (pp. 852006-852006), International Society for Optics and Photonics.
- [7] Hyde, M. W., Wyman, J. E., & Tyler, G. A. (2014). "Rigorous investigation of the array-tilt aberration for hexagonal, optical phased arrays", Applied optics, 53(11), 2416-2424.
- [8] Van Zandt, N. R., Cusumano, S. J., Bartell, R. J., Basu S., McCrae, J. E., Fiorino, S. T., "Comparison of coherent and incoherent laser beam combination for tactical engagements", Opt. Eng. 51(10), 104301 (2012).

BIOGRAPHIES

Jack McCrae received his Ph.D. in Physics from the Air Force Institute of Technology in 1997, an M.S. in Physics (Optics) from the Air Force Institute of Technology in 1993, and a B.S. in Physics from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1984.

He is a retired Air Force Colonel with 27 years of service and currently with the Center for Directed Energy as a Research Assistant Professor in the Engineering Physics Department at AFIT. His research interests include optics, lasers, quantum and non-linear optics, laser radar, atmospheric propagation and imaging.

Steven T. Fiorino received his BS degrees in geography and meteorology from Ohio State (1987) and Florida State (1989) universities. He additionally holds an MS in atmospheric dynamics from Ohio State (1993) and a PhD in physical meteorology from Florida State (2002). He is a retired

Air Force Lieutenant Colonel with 21 years of service and currently a research associate professor of atmospheric physics within the Engineering Physics Department at AFIT and is the director of the Center for Directed Energy. His research interests include microwave remote sensing, development of weather signal processing algorithms, and atmospheric effects on military systems such as high-energy lasers and weapons of mass destruction. Dr. Fiorino is a member of SPIE, AMS, AIAA and DEPS.